

The Impacts of the Economic Crisis in Italy: The Number of Bankruptcy Cases and the Sectors Most Affected

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Abstract

This empirical research tries to represent the many numbers of the phenomenon and of the insolvency procedures in Italy from 2012 to 2019. The analysis first involved the country and then the attention was paid to the Regions and partly also to the Provinces, given the impact of the number of bankruptcy procedures on the number of active companies, on new members and on those removed. For each year, both at national and regional level, after the macro-disaggregated data of insolvency proceedings and non-bankruptcy proceedings, the study involved both companies and regions/provinces. In particular, the country annually highlights the region and sector of economic activity that recorded the highest number of bankruptcies, bankruptcy and non-insolvency proceedings. For the sake of completeness, the table shows all the data, both by region and by economic activity, distinguished between bankruptcy procedures and non-bankruptcy procedures. Furthermore, the percentage incidence on the national total is highlighted on several occasions. At the regional level, for each year, the same methodology adopted at national level was replicated and therefore the individual provinces were also considered in relation to the opening of insolvency, bankruptcy and non-insolvency procedures. As mentioned, the relationship between the number of open competitive procedures and the number of companies, re-registered and removed was also considered.

Keyword: BusinessCrisis, Bankruptcy, Insolvency Proceedings, Economic Activities

Introduction

The economic crisis has led to numerous bankruptcies in Italy, as well as in other European countries.

The risk of bankruptcy is linked to several factors, some financial, others economic.

In the first case, some examples of risk are: a bad management of immediate cash; an excessive delay in the collection of receivables as well as the insolvency of counterparties; the difficulty of realizing the warehouse going to weigh down the immobilized activities. There is no doubt that excessive use of debt rather than risk capital could have very negative repercussions, as could the incorrect composition of the sources of finance.

In the second case: revenues could be below expectations and not even enough to cover fixed costs; the characteristic management could lead to lower results than the extra characteristic; as well as excessive indebtedness involves high interest payments and so on.

Companies need to calculate and avoid these risks; otherwise they could go into crisis and then go bankrupt.

The present work studies how many bankruptcies and business crises have been in Italy from 2012 to 2019, also highlighted the sectors that have been most affected; in addition, the attention is directed to this last year and also to the individual regions (Lombardy, Lazio and Campania).

Search results

The aim of empirical research is to investigate in detail the phenomenon of competition procedures in Italy from 2012 to 2019.

Such an extended period has allowed to bring out what happened in the year 2014, year of turning considered the change of direction intervened, as it is better said later; In addition, before 2012, a document deficiency emerged which did not allow comparison with the most up-to-date data.

The phenomenon has followed a fluctuating trend, since from the year 2012 to 2014, it has been increasing; from 2014 to 2018, decreasing and in 2019 were recorded data like 2018, as represented in the graph below.

The most significant change was between 2012 and 2013 where the increase was 16%; overall, the change between 2012 and 2019 was down by 13%, in the table the details:

YEARS	N. PROCEDURES	ABSOLUTE N.	PERCENTAGE N.	NOTE
2012	13.896	-	-	-
2013	16.062	2.166	15,6%	Increase
2014	17.725	1.663	10,4%	Increase
2015	16.540	-1.185	-6,7%	Decrease
2016	14.542	-1.998	-12,1%	Decrease
2017	13.098	-1.444	-9,9%	Decrease
2018	12.083	-1.015	-7,7%	Decrease
2019	12.039	-44	-0,4%	Decrease

In the period considered, the activated bankruptcies procedures have been in average approximately 14,500; so distributed: in the regions of NORTH-WEST approximately 4,400, in those of NORTH-EAST approximately 2,800, to the CENTER approximately 3,500, in the SOUTH approximately 2,600 and in the ISLANDS approximately 590.

The non-bankruptcy procedures (also called "*other insolvency procedures*") represented on average about 15% of the total of the procedures. From the analysis of the data, it emerges that in Calabria this ratio was the highest compared to other regions, reaching even 40% in some years; while, in Campania it was almost always the lowest.

In the observation period, the region that recorded the highest number of bankruptcies procedures was always Lombardy followed by Lazio and Veneto (this ranking has been maintained for all years except for 2019 where Tuscany has passed the Veneto). In the following table is represented the ranking by average number of bankruptcies procedures activated in the period depending on the Region.

REGIONS	BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES	<i>bankruptcies</i>	<i>no bankruptcies</i>
Lombardy	3.070	2.705	366
Lazio	1.623	1.426	197
Veneto	1.253	1.070	184
Tuscany	1.177	960	217
Emilia-Romagna	1.094	903	191
Campania	1.049	954	95
Piedmont	982	835	147
Sicily	885	746	140

Apulia	636	534	102
The Marches	487	395	92
Calabria	430	278	152
Abruzzo	328	265	63
Liguria	325	252	73
Sardinia	298	266	31
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	265	204	61
Umbria	260	211	49
Trentino-Alto Adige	189	157	32
Basilicata	66	54	12
Molise	62	47	15
Valle d'Aosta	20	15	5
ITALY	14.498	12.276	2.222

(average values in descending order for BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES)

By analysing the impact that this phenomenon has had on the various sectors of activity, it emerges that the most affected were wholesale and retail trade, construction and manufacturing activities, as detailed below.

Economic Activities	BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES	<i>bankruptcies</i>	<i>no bankruptcies</i>
G - Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	3.270	2.916	353
F - Construction	2.894	2.478	417
C - Manufacturing	2.842	2.360	482
X - Unclassified companies	982	874	108
I - Accommodation and food service activities	797	742	55
H -Transportation and storage	761	596	165
L - Real estate activities	750	630	119
N - Administrative and support service activities	516	401	114
M - Professional, scientific and technical activities	463	395	68
J- Information and communication	303	265	39
R- Arts, entertainment and recreation	178	149	30
A- Agriculture, forestry and fishing	172	86	86
Q - Human health and social work activities	163	70	93
S - Other service activities	128	109	19
K -Financial and insurance activities	100	73	28
E -Water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities	77	57	20
P - Education	49	34	16
B- Mining and quarrying	28	22	6
D- Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	27	21	7
TOTAL	14.498	12.276	2.222

(average values in descending order for BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES)

The imported links are:

- the ratio between the number of open procedures and active companies is on average less than 0.3%;
- the ratio between the number of open procedures and new companies was on average about 4%;
- the ratio between the number of open procedures and discontinued companies was on average about 3%.

In 2019 the insolvency procedures opened in Italy were n. 12,039 of which: n. 10,542 bankruptcies (88% of the national total of insolvency proceedings); n. 1,497 non-bankruptcy procedures (12% of the national total of bankruptcy procedures). Compared to the previous year, bankruptcy procedures decreased by no. 44 (approximately nil decrease); bankruptcies decreased by n. 6 (approximately zero decrease); non-bankruptcy insolvency proceedings decreased by no. 38 (decrease of 3%). The region that recorded the highest number of insolvency proceedings; of bankruptcies and non-bankruptcy procedures was LOMBARDIA with: n. 2,576 bankruptcy procedures (21% of the national total of bankruptcy procedures); n. 2,338 bankruptcies

(22% of the national total of bankruptcies); n. 238 non-bankruptcy bankruptcy proceedings (16% of the national total of non-bankruptcy bankruptcy proceedings). The sector with the highest number of insolvency proceedings and bankruptcies was the wholesale and retail trade with n. 2,736 bankruptcy procedures (23% of the national total of bankruptcy procedures) and no. 2,551 bankruptcies (24% of the national total of bankruptcies). The sector with the highest number of openings of non-bankruptcy procedures was the construction with n. 276 (18% of the national total of non-bankruptcy proceedings).

In order to highlight the phenomenon at a regional level, the data of Lombardy, Lazio and Campania are very important because they represent respectively the North, the Centre and the South of Italy.

The performance of the insolvency proceedings who is registered in Lombardy was the same as the national average. The open procedures have been on average about 3,000 distributed as follows:

The sectors that have suffered most of this phenomenon, as nationwide, were the manufacturing, construction and wholesale and retail. From 2012 to 2013 the leadership was recorded by the manufacturing sector; from 2014 to 2018 the most affected sector was the construction sector, finally in 2019 the trade recorded the highest number of insolvency proceedings compared to all the others.

The ratio between active companies and companies subject to insolvency proceedings does not reach 1%; In fact, it was an average of about 0.4% (slightly higher percentage than the national average).

At the provincial level what is shown in the table emerges; Milan is the city that keeps track of multiple procedures.

LOMBARDY	BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES	<i>bankruptcies</i>	<i>no bankruptcies</i>
Milan	1.367	1.215	152
Brescia	324	290	35
Bergamo	316	275	41
Monza e Brianza	231	209	22
Varese	223	194	29
Como	155	137	17
Mantova	120	97	23
Pavia	118	107	11
Lecco	81	66	15
Cremona	69	60	10
Lodi	49	43	6
Sondrio	17	14	3
TOTAL	3.070	2.705	366

(average values in descending order for BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES)

The trend of the selection procedures in Lazio was the same as that national, although the decrease from 2015 to 2019 was less significant. The open procedures were on average about 1,600, with a percentage equal to that of Lombardy and therefore distributed as follows:

The sectors that have suffered most of this phenomenon, in contrast to what has emerged at national level, were: wholesale and retail trade, followed by construction and that of non-classified businesses.

The ratio between active companies and companies subject to insolvency procedures, as in Lombardy, does not reach 1%; in fact, it was on average about 0.3%.

At the provincial level as it emerges in the table; Rome is the city that registers the bankruptcy proceedings.

LAZIO	BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES	<i>bankruptcies</i>	<i>no bankruptcies</i>
Rome	1.335	1.175	160
Frosinone	104	89	15
Latina	136	124	13
Rieti	17	13	4
Viterbo	30	24	6
TOTAL	1.623	1.426	197

(average values in descending order for BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES)

The trend of insolvency procedures that was recorded in Campania was the same as the national one until 2018; However, it should be noted that between 2018 and 2019 there was an increase in live. The open procedures were on average about 1,000 distributed as follows, there is a lower weight of non-bankruptcy insolvency procedures:

The sectors that were most affected by this phenomenon, as it emerged at the national level, were: wholesale and retail trade, manufacturing and construction. In this regard would point out that the trade sector has always maintained the primacy, unlike the other two sectors that are mutually held the second and third place.

The ratio between active companies and companies subject to insolvency procedures, as for Lombardy and Lazio, does not reach 1%; in fact, it was on average about 0.2%.

At the provincial level as it emerges in the table; Naples is the city that records the most bankruptcy proceedings.

CAMPANIA	BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES	<i>bankruptcies</i>	<i>no bankruptcies</i>
Napoli	573	539	34
Avellino	84	76	8
Benevento	73	62	11
Caserta	133	115	18
Salerno	187	163	24
TOTAL	1.049	954	95

(average values in descending order for BANKRUPTCIES PROCEDURES)

Conclusions

In Italy, during the period studied, there have been many failures; even if they are decreasing. To resolve crisis situations, bankruptcy is the most followed route since no use of the other tools has been detected. The percentage of active companies and bankrupt companies is very low, the proportion of companies in crisis and new companies / deleted companies is higher. The sectors most affected are wholesale and retail trade, manufacturing and construction, which have recorded imported numbers of bankruptcies. Another sector that recorded a considerable number of bankruptcy proceedings was that of “unclassified companies”.

Lombardy, Lazio and Campania, as shown, provide a closer look at the Italian insolvency procedures highlighting the regional differences.